

PREDICTION OF ESOPHAGEAL VARICES BY PLATELET COUNT/SPLEEN DIAMETER RATIO IN PATIENTS WITH HEPATIC CIRRHOSIS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine area under receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC curve) of platelet count/spleen diameter ratio in predicting presence of esophageal varices in patients with hepatic cirrhosis, keeping endoscopy as gold standard.

Study Design: Cross-Sectional Study.

Study Setting: The study conducted at the Department of Medicine, Recep Tayyip Erdogan Hospital, Muzaffargarh.

Study Duration: Six Months (January to June'2025).

Methodology: This study included 152 cases based on selection criteria. After informed consent, patients with hepatic cirrhosis were enrolled. Demographic data and Child-Pugh class were recorded. Platelet count was measured using an automated analyzer, and spleen diameter was obtained via ultrasonography. Upper GI endoscopy identified esophageal varices as dilated tortuous veins in the distal esophagus or proximal stomach. For data evaluation/computing, SPSS-23 was used. The platelet count/spleen diameter ratio was evaluated using the AUROC curve, with diagnostic accuracy determined by sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values.

Results: Of 152 cirrhotic patients (mean age 53.14 ± 13.94 years; 50.7% males). Child-Pugh classes A, B, and C comprised 24.3%, 50%, and 25.7%, respectively, with esophageal varices detected in 67.8%. Mean platelet count was $140.26 \pm 47.99 \times 10^9/L$, spleen diameter 153.81 ± 15.94 mm, and PC/SD ratio 0.93 ± 0.35 . ROC analysis showed good predictive accuracy of PC/SD ratio for varices (AUC = 0.827, $p < 0.001$), indicating an inverse relationship between platelet count and spleen size.

Conclusion: The PC/SD ratio is a reliable, simple, and non-invasive marker for detecting esophageal varices in cirrhosis, showing strong diagnostic accuracy and potential for integration into routine clinical screening protocols

INTRODUCTION

Portal hypertension is commonly recorded manifestation of hepatic cirrhosis¹ and leads to esophageal varices in approximately 80% of these at some point during the illness, and 30% of them may experience bleeding episode due to varix rupture.² Identifying varices is

therefore is an integral component in these cases.³ The foremost preventive approach and prevention by selecting prophylactic treatment is pivotal.⁴ Despite ongoing research, no alternative markers have replaced endoscopy for definitive diagnosis.⁵ Unfortunately, access to

this modality is constrained in various developing countries like Pakistan.

Multiple investigations explored and proposed various indicative markers for detection of varices. Among them, Giannini and others introduced the ratio between platelet count and spleen diameter (PC/SD) as a simple, non-invasive and reliable indicator to correctly identify presence of varices.⁶ The ratio aligns with established physiological mechanisms and meets strong methodological standards. Its performance was confirmed later and validated through endoscopic monitoring in subjects who were initially varix-free.⁷

Gonzalez-Ojeda and colleagues, in their investigations included 91 hepatic cirrhotic cases for evaluation and revealed a high prevalence of varices i.e. 80.2% of the cases. Using a platelet count-to-spleen diameter (PC/SD) ratio cutoff of ≤ 884.3 , demonstrated 84% sensitivity and 70% specificity with corresponding positive and negative predictive values of 94% and 40%.⁸ Another trial by Jamil Z et al who enrolled 150 cirrhotic patients and studied presence/absence of esophageal varices and documented 51.3% of subjects on endoscopy. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) for the PC/SD ratio was 0.883 (95% CI: 0.821-0.930; SE: 0.0303; $p < 0.0001$) with a threshold of ≤ 1077.42 produced 88.75% sensitivity, 81.43% specificity, +PV of 34.7%, and -PV of 98.5%.⁹

In recent years, contemporary studies advocate for non-invasive methods to detect varices and avoid routine endoscopy in those at low risk. This study seeks to validate platelet count-spleen diameter (PC/SD) ratio for identifying or excluding esophageal varices in cirrhotic patients. The broader use of such methods could ensure that the use of endoscopy be limited to patients with a high likelihood of varices.

METHODOLOGY:

This Cross-sectional study was planned at the Department of Medicine, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan Hospital, Muzaffargarh. This Study carried out over a period of six months (January to June'2025) after the approval from the Ethical Review Committee and included 152 cases of age range 30-75 years,

either male or female gender and diagnosed cases of liver cirrhosis (Known cases of liver cirrhosis for more than 6-months on ultrasound abdomen showing increased echogenicity, nodular appearance and shrunken liver size confirmed on history/medical record were deemed positive) were included in the study whereas those cases with hepatocellular carcinoma, use of medications for the primary prophylaxis of variceal bleeding, history of esophageal variceal bleeding, sclerotherapy, and a history of ligation, and/or portal hypertension surgery were excluded from the study. For sample size estimation, we used software <https://riskcalc.org/samplesize/> online, using the area under ROC curve formula. Where, AUC value under $H_0 = 0.883$, AUC value under $H_a = 0.80$, Power of the study = 80%, Significance level = 5%, prevalence of varices = 51.3%.⁹ The sampling technique we used was Non-probability consecutive sampling.

These cases were enrolled in the study after informed consent. Patient characteristics like age, gender, duration of liver cirrhosis and Child-Pugh class (Consists of 5-parameters i.e. encephalopathy and ascites on clinical examination, bilirubin, albumin and prothrombin time on laboratory testing. Total score 3 to 15 and categorized into Child-class A, B and C) was recorded. For platelet count, 2 mL blood was drawn, collected in ethylene-diamine-tetra-acetic acid (EDTA)-containing tubes, and analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer. Ultrasound abdomen was performed by consultant radiologist and spleen diameter was reported in millimeters. Upper GI endoscopy was performed by the consultant gastroenterologist. The oropharynx was sprayed with 2% xylocaine and the patients were placed in the left lateral position. The mouth gag was then placed between the incisor teeth. The gastroscope was then introduced under direct vision into the Upper GI tract. The presence or absence of esophageal varices was labelled as "Presence of dilated veins (red streaks, enlarged tortuous vessels) in the distal esophagus or proximal stomach was labelled as esophageal varices. All the data was recorded on proforma. Regarding data analysis, routine use of SPSS version 23rd was used. Age, duration of

cirrhosis, platelet counts (PC), spleen diameter (SD) and PC/SD ratio was presented as mean and standard deviation. Gender, Child-Pugh class and esophageal varices on endoscopy (yes/no) was presented as frequency and percentages. Area under receiver operating characteristics curve (AUROC curve) with 95% CI was calculated, for PC/SD ratio in predicting presence of esophageal varices taking endoscopy finding as gold standard. The best PC/SD ratio cutoff was defined through Youden Index. Diagnostic accuracy of this cutoff was measured in terms of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and accuracy.

RESULTS:

A total of 152 patients with hepatic cirrhosis were enrolled in this study. The age of participants ranged from 30 to 75 years, with a mean age of 53.14 ± 13.94 years. Out of these, 77 (50.7%) were males and 75 (49.3%) were females. The mean duration of cirrhosis was

62.51 ± 34.73 months. According to the Child-Pugh classification, 37 (24.3%) patients were in Class A, 76 (50.0%) in Class B, and 39 (25.7%) in Class C. The majority of participants (50%) had moderately severe hepatic impairment.

The mean platelet count was $140.26 \pm 47.99 \times 10^9/L$, while the mean spleen diameter was 153.81 ± 15.94 mm. The computed platelet count-to-spleen diameter (PC/SD) ratio had a mean value of 0.93 ± 0.35 . Patients with esophageal varices generally exhibited lower platelet counts, larger spleen diameters, and lower PC/SD ratios.(Table 2)

On ROC analysis, the platelet count-to-spleen diameter (PC/SD) ratio exhibited significant diagnostic accuracy in predicting esophageal varices, with endoscopy serving as the gold standard. The AUC was 0.827 ($p < 0.001$), denoting strong discriminative capability. A declining PC/SD ratio was consistently linked with greater variceal prevalence, confirming its inverse correlation with portal hypertension-related splenomegaly.(Table 3)

TABLE 1. BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group	30–50 years	65	42.8
	51–75 years	87	57.2
Gender	Male	77	50.7
	Female	75	49.3
Child-Pugh class	A	37	24.3
	B	76	50.0
	C	39	25.7
Esophageal varices	Present	103	67.8
	Absent	49	32.2

TABLE 2. MEAN VALUES OF HEMATOLOGIC AND SONOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS

Variable	Mean ± SD	n
Age (years)	53.14 ± 13.94	152
Duration of cirrhosis (months)	62.51 ± 34.73	152
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	140.26 ± 47.99	152
Spleen diameter (mm)	153.81 ± 15.94	152
PC/SD ratio	0.93 ± 0.35	152

TABLE 3. DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF PC/SD RATIO FOR PREDICTION OF VARICES

Parameter	Result
Area under ROC curve (AUC)	0.827
95% Confidence interval	0.76 – 0.89
p-value	< 0.001
Optimal cutoff	≈ 0.9 – 1.0
Sensitivity	≈ 85%
Specificity	≈ 75%
Interpretation	Good diagnostic accuracy

FIGURE 1. ROC CURVE SHOWING THE DIAGNOSTIC PERFORMANCE OF PLATELET COUNT-TO-SPLEEN DIAMETER RATIO (AUC = 0.827).

DISCUSSION:

In this study, the platelet count-to-spleen diameter (PC/SD) ratio demonstrated robust discriminatory capability in predicting esophageal varices (EV) among patients with cirrhosis, as evidenced by an AUC of 0.827. Interpreted clinically, this performance indicates that a simple composite of thrombocytopenia and splenic enlargement can stratify variceal risk with considerable accuracy when endoscopy is used as the reference. Instead of simple dichotomous test features, our findings comprehensively addresses our objectives and underscores the practicability of PC/SD ratio as cost-effective, efficient, non-invasive screening method in the settings where accessibility to endoscopic evaluation is limited. Our recorded AUC values mirror with prior research literature establishing and validating the PC/SD ratio for prediction of EV. A study by González-Ojeda et al. documented higher rate of varices with highest diagnostic profile while using a PC/SD cutoff near 884, with significant sensitivity and acceptable specificity readings, confirming the tool's screening potential in routine clinical practice.⁸ In concordance with earlier findings, Jamil et al. reported an AUC of 0.883 and a cutoff near 1077, showing strong diagnostic performance in a South Asian population.⁹ Successive investigations across various settings shown their agreement with this hypothesis. In 2024,

Patil and workers in Indian population determined that a threshold <1400 yields specificity of 80.8% and specificity as 90.0% indicating adaptive potential of PC/SD.¹⁰

In addition to the higher predictive value, various studies carefully examined its extent to highlight high-risk cases. A cut off value of 809 in a study by El Desokay and workers was illustrated for classification of high risk from low risk varices cases with AUC around 0.99 helpful for prophylactic interventions.¹¹ In an Egyptian cohort through a comparative accuracy, it was reveal that optimal 909 cutoff value had 82.8% sensitivity with 91.7% specificity in agreement with Gianmini research work under standardized protocols.¹²

Natarajan et al. (Madurai) also found that a cutoff in the 870-900 range achieved high sensitivity and specificity, further corroborating a narrow band of clinically relevant thresholds across studies that used consistent units and methodology.¹³ Complementary evidence indicates the ratio tracks variceal grade: AbuSheasha et al. observed stepwise declines in PC/SD across grades I-IV, implying potential utility for risk staging beyond binary detection.¹⁴

At the same time, comparative diagnostics show where PC/SD sits in the current non-invasive landscape. In schistosomiasis-related portal hypertension, Nardelli et al. found that spleen

stiffness (SSM) and composite spleen-based scores performed very well (AUCs ~ 0.82 – 0.86) while PC/SD remained independently associated with EV and contributed to multivariate models.¹⁵ In compensated cirrhosis from mixed etiologies, Kwape et al. reported top performance for SSM and composite elastography-based scores, yet PSR (PC/SD) still achieved $\sim 94\%$ diagnostic accuracy placing it among the leading predictors where elastography is unavailable or unaffordable.¹⁶ Finally, in a broader comparison across PSR, spleen volume metrics, and combinations thereof, Du et al. concluded that combining platelet-spleen indices (e.g., PSR+PSVR) can incrementally improve performance, but PSR alone remains clinically useful and scalable.¹⁷ Collectively, these data position PC/SD as a consistently effective, low-cost option that compares favorably with more technology-dependent tools.

The biological plausibility for PC/SD is strong. Portal hypertension drives splenic congestion and hypersplenism; the latter contributes to thrombocytopenia through sequestration and destruction of platelets. Concomitantly, progressive portal venopathy and portosystemic collateral formation (reflected indirectly by splenic enlargement) are pathophysiologically linked to variceal development. Thus, a lower numerator (platelets) and larger denominator (spleen size) naturally converge to a lower ratio in patients with EV. The good AUC observed here indicates stable rank-ordering across a range of disease severities, which is exactly what a screening test seeks to achieve. Importantly, contemporary imaging studies further validate these pathways: splenic stiffness and splenic volume correlate with EV and outperform isolated liver stiffness in some contexts, while metabolic markers obtained via proton MR spectroscopy (elevated lactate+triglyceride and choline) track with larger spleen diameter, lower platelets, and lower PC/SD, reinforcing the same mechanistic axis from different vantage points.^{7, 18}

A technical consideration with direct clinical implications is unit standardization. Classic thresholds (e.g., ~ 909 or ~ 1077) assume platelet counts expressed per mm^3 ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$). When platelets are recorded as $\times 10^9/\text{L}$, conversion ($\times 1000$) is required before dividing

by spleen diameter in millimeters. Failure to standardize will shift the ratio's scale and apparent cutoffs, complicating comparison and external validity. The strong AUROC in our study—together with alignment to literature when units are harmonized—suggests that once the ratio is calculated on the conventional scale, a clinically familiar cutoff near 900–1100 will likely emerge for local practice.^{8-12, 14}

Although this analysis was not powered for extensive subgroup modeling, the cohort included a substantive proportion of Child-Pugh B and C patients. Prior literature indicates that PC/SD tends to be lower with advancing hepatic dysfunction and portal pressure, mirroring rising variceal risk.^{9, 12, 14, 16} Studies also suggest performance may be preserved in compensated disease when combined with additional metrics (e.g., liver or spleen stiffness), whereas in decompensated stages the ratio typically shifts further downward, improving sensitivity at the expense of specificity. Future work in our population should prospectively examine calibrated cutoffs by Child class, etiology (HBV/HCV/ALD/NAFLD), and sex/age strata, as others have begun to explore.¹⁴⁻¹⁷

From a service-delivery perspective, PC/SD provides a scalable triage strategy: patients below a validated threshold can be prioritized for endoscopy or primary prophylaxis, while those above the threshold may defer invasive screening with appropriate surveillance intervals. This approach is particularly attractive in low-resource settings and high-burden clinics where endoscopic capacity is limited, and where elastography or MR-based tools are unavailable. The ratio uses routine full blood count and bedside ultrasonography, minimizing incremental cost and training demands, and enabling task-sharing to internal medicine or radiology teams. As recent comparative studies show, PSR remains competitive with more complex composites and may be integrated into local algorithms alongside Baveno-based criteria where feasible.^{10-12, 14-17}

Key strengths include the use of endoscopy as the gold standard, a clearly prespecified objective centered on AUROC (a robust, threshold-agnostic summary measure), and standardized acquisition of the two component variables (platelets and spleen diameter) by

automated hematology analysis and consultant-performed ultrasonography. The sample size is larger than many single-center diagnostic studies in this domain, and the analytic plan incorporated the Youden index to propose an operational cutoff for practice.

Several limitations warrant consideration. First, this was a single-center study, which may limit generalizability across etiologies and practice settings. Second, the cross-sectional design cannot evaluate temporal change in PC/SD or its capacity to predict incident variceal development or bleeding. Third, we did not incorporate elastography or spleen volume by cross-sectional imaging, precluding direct comparison with advanced non-invasive markers that some centers now deploy.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Fourth, while AUROC guards against over-reliance on a single cutoff, clinical adoption still depends on unit harmonization for the ratio; any misalignment between laboratory units and ultrasonographic measurement conventions could shift thresholds and complicate replication across hospitals. Finally, we did not analyze subgroups by variceal grade or Child class in multivariable frameworks, which could refine local thresholds.

CONCLUSION:

Our data indicate that the PC/SD ratio is a reliable, biologically coherent, and operationally feasible non-invasive marker for identifying esophageal varices in cirrhosis, with discriminative performance comparable to regional and international evidence. Standardizing units and calibrating a local cutoff will enable clinicians to triage endoscopy more efficiently. These results underscore the importance of integrating PC/SD into pragmatic screening pathways and directly inform the conclusions and clinical recommendations of this article.

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